

Heat Stress Assessment Among Outdoor Brick Molders in Umuagwo and its Environs

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Abstract: Heat stress poses a significant occupational hazard, especially for outdoor workers engaged in strenuous activities like brick molding. This study investigates the prevalence of heat stress among outdoor brick molders in Umuagwo and its environs, assessing their knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to heat stress self-assessment. A structured questionnaire was used for data collection in this study during the dry season (hot weather). The questionnaire was designed to gather comprehensive information on various aspects related to heat stress self-assessment among outdoor brick molders (n = 106). The survey findings reveal that the brick molders are all male (100%). The respondents (74.5%) are married while 25.5% are single. The brick molders (56.8%) are in their active ages (41-50), and 79.2% of the respondents have only primary school education while 20.8% have secondary school education. The result also shows that 61.5% of the respondents have been into brick molding for the past 6-10 years, and 64.2% of the respondents work for at least 8 hours daily. Majority of the respondents (93.4%) prefer to work in the morning. The result also reveal that only 13.2% of the respondents wear improvise personal protective equipment's (PPEs), while 86.8% do not wear. Findings from the personal experiences of the respondents show that 92.5% of them do not think heat stress impact is avoidable, 94.3% of the respondents agreed that heat stress has impact on their body, while 96.2% of the respondents have experienced one or two symptoms of heat stress. 96.2% of the respondents have experienced heat stress induced sickness, 93.4% of the respondents go for self-medication due to sickness induced by heat stress. It was observed from the survey that 81.1% of the respondents agreed that heat stress reduces the number of bricks they make in a day, 91.5% of the respondents feel very hot when working during heat wave. These brick molders experience heat stress due to the demanding nature of their work, the findings highlight the need for urgent action to address heat stress and protect the health and well-being of these workers.

Keywords: Heat stress, brick molders, outdoor, climate change, health

Introduction

Heat stress occurs when the body's ability to regulate its internal temperature is overwhelmed by external heat, leading to a range of adverse health effects, from mild discomfort to severe conditions like heatstroke (Taylor et al., 2016). The consequences of heat stress extend beyond immediate health impacts, affecting productivity, increasing the risk of accidents, and imposing economic burdens on workers and employers (Sario et al., 2023). The occupational settings, especially in low- and middle-income countries, often lack appropriate guidelines and heat management systems, exacerbating the problem (Lucas et al., 2014). The confluence of rising global temperatures due to climate change and the physically demanding nature of brick molding further intensifies the risk (Lucas et al., 2014). Vulnerable populations with limited capacity to adapt are often overlooked in broader heat stress exposure assessments (Ramsay et al., 2021). Occupational health issues stemming from heat have been a long-standing concern, particularly for occupations that involve intense physical labor or exposure to elevated temperatures (Zander et al., 2018). Heat stress represents a significant occupational health risk, particularly for individuals engaged in strenuous outdoor activities such as brick molding. Workers in sun-exposed

environments often face work-related discomfort and health issues in hot weather, highlighting the economic and social burdens imposed by temperature conditions on enterprises (Zhang et al., 2023). These workers often face prolonged exposure to high ambient temperatures, coupled with physical exertion, increasing their susceptibility to heat-related illnesses (Owhor et al., 2021).

Outdoor brick molders are particularly vulnerable to heat stress due to the demanding nature of their work, which involves prolonged exposure to the sun and high temperatures, coupled with intense physical activity (Venugopal et al., 2021). The urban heat island effect, coupled with physical work, individual differences, and the context of developing countries where technological solutions are often lacking, are the main factors that exacerbate heat stress in the workplace (Lundgren et al., 2013). The absence of adequate preventative measures and a lack of awareness among workers and employers further compound the problem. Many outdoor workers undertake multiple jobs and may be at risk of other occupational hazards (John & Jha, 2023).

The brick molding industry in Umuagwo and its environs is characterized by labor-intensive practices, with workers often toiling for extended hours under direct sunlight. The lack of awareness, combined

with limited access to resources and preventive measures, creates a significant risk of heat-related illnesses among these workers. There is a growing concern about the environmental and climate change impacts on the population's health, especially since the late 1990s (Xiang et al., 2013). Understanding the magnitude of heat stress and evaluating the effectiveness of self-assessment strategies are essential for developing targeted interventions. Hence, this study of heat stress assessment among outdoor brick molders in Umuagwo and its environs.

Effective strategies for mitigating heat-related health risks encompass a range of interventions implemented at the individual, building, and urban scales (Jay et al., 2021). The evaluation of heat stress and the implementation of effective self-assessment strategies are crucial for protecting the health and well-being of these workers. These strategies may include training programs, engineering controls, and policy interventions (Jackson & Rosenberg, 2010). Also a multifaceted approach integrating ergonomic improvements, comprehensive heat stress management strategies, and a focus on maintaining worker health is essential to mitigating the risks associated with brick molding (Lucas et al., 2014).

Materials and Methods

Study Design

This study employed a cross-sectional research design to assess heat stress among outdoor brick molders in Umuagwo and its environs.

Study Area

Umuagwo and its environs, located in Imo State, Nigeria, serve as the study area for this research. A field study was carried out in Umuagwo and its environs in Ohaji Egbema L.G.A. of Imo State where average annual precipitation is in excess of 2,500 mm, while temperature ranges between 26°C and 30°C (NIMET, 2014) and the ambient temperature can reach 94⁰ F during the dry season. Umuagwo lies within the tropical rainforest zone with rainy season between April and October and dry season between November and March. The area is characterized by a predominantly hot and humid climate, particularly during the dry season, making it susceptible to heat waves. Brick molding is a common occupation (mainly for the male folks) in Umuagwo and the South East region at large, providing livelihood for a significant portion of the population.

Study Population

The study population consist of all outdoor brick molders working in brick molding sites within Umuagwo and its environs. Brick molders were selected based on their

direct involvement in the brick molding process and their exposure to outdoor conditions. The study was carried out in February – March (dry/hot season). Brick-molding process and impact to the peri-urban environment exposed significantly to high physical risk to the workers. Sample size was determined using statistical formulas, considering the population size.

Ethical Clearance

Ethical approval was granted by the Research and Ethics Committee of the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State with approval number: UAES/URC/EAC/0011, to ensure adherence to ethical research principles. Written consent was given by the participant and also permission was obtained from the management of the brick molding sites to facilitate access to the study population and ensure cooperation during the data collection process.

Sample Size and Data Collection

A total of one hundred and six ($n = 106$) brick molders was used in the survey. Data was collected using structured questionnaires administered to brick molders. The questionnaire was designed to gather comprehensive information on various aspects related to heat stress assessment among outdoor brick molders. They responded to the questionnaire and

their responds were recorded. The questionnaire included sections on demographic characteristics (age, gender, education level), work practices (work hours, breaks, hydration habits), and self-reported symptoms of heat stress (headache, dizziness, fatigue).

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

To ensure the collection of relevant and reliable data, clearly defined inclusion and exclusion criteria was established. The inclusion criteria specify that participants must be actively involved in outdoor brick molding activities at the sites. The study excluded individuals not directly involved in brick molding.

Data Analysis

The collected data was subjected to statistical analysis using appropriate software packages. Descriptive statistics, such as frequencies, percentages and means was computed to summarize the characteristics of the study population and the prevalence of heat stress.

Results and Discussion

The result gotten from field, shows that brick molders in Umuagwo and its environs are all male (100%), this is because brick molding is a very tedious job and requires a lot of energy. Additionally, 74.5% of the respondents are married, while 25.5% are single. A significant proportion (56.8%) falls within the 41–50 age bracket,

indicating that most brick molders are in their economically active years. Regarding educational attainment, 79.2% of the respondents have only primary education, and 20.8% have completed secondary education. This relatively low level of

formal education may limit their access to formal or white-collar employment opportunities, thereby influencing their participation in brick molding as a viable means of livelihood.

Table 1 Questionnaire Results from Brick Molders in Umuagwo and Its Environs (n = 106)

Category	Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender of Respondents	Male	106	100.0
	Female	0	0.0
Marital Status	Married	79	74.5
	Single	27	25.5
Age Distribution	21–30 years	4	3.8
	31–40 years	28	26.4
	41–50 years	60	56.8
	51–60 years	14	13.0
Level of Education	Primary	84	79.2
	Secondary	22	20.8
Years of Experience	1–5 years	33	31.0
	6–10 years	65	61.5
	11–15 years	8	7.5
Daily Work Duration	6 hours	3	2.8
	7 hours	32	30.2
	8 hours	68	64.2
	9 hours	3	2.8
Break Taken During Work	Yes	106	100.0
Knowledge of Heat Stress	Yes	28	26.4
	No	78	73.6
Preferred Work Period	Morning	99	93.4
	Afternoon	7	6.6
Use of PPEs (Improvised)	Yes	21	13.2
	No	85	86.8

The result also shows that 61.5% of the respondents have been into brick molding for the past 6-10 years, indicating that they have acquired enough experience in the business. 64.2% of the respondents work for 8 hours daily, this is a long period of time as they are paid based on the number of bricks molded or the number of bags of cement utilized per day and they are exposed to heat stress for that long as they are trying to get enough money to meet up with their family needs as majority (74.5%) of the workers are married. All the respondents go for break, which could be a coping mechanism to reduce or minimize the effect of heat stress. Also, 73.6% of the respondents do not have knowledge of heat stress, this is because most of them do not have enough education, so they are ignorant of the dangers of heat stress. Furthermore, 93.4% of the respondents prefer to work in the morning, this is because the heat is not too much in the morning compared to afternoon. Only 13.2% of the respondents wear improvised PPEs, while 86.8% do not wear, and majority of them wear only shorts without any shirt to cover their body, thereby exposing themselves to heat stress and its health effects, as these PPEs are meant to protect them from the hazards of the job.

The personal experiences of the workers, as presented in Table 2, reveal a troubling trend. A majority (92.5%) believe that the impact of heat stress is unavoidable, while 94.3%

report that it affects their bodies. Alarming, 96.2% have experienced symptoms associated with heat stress. This high incidence may be attributed to inadequate protective measures—such as the lack of personal protective equipment (PPEs)—and prolonged exposure to extreme weather conditions, likely intensified by ongoing climate change. Also 96.2% of the respondents have experienced heat stress induced sickness, and 93.4% of the respondents go for self-medication due to heat stress, which is a very wrong practice because they are not qualified to prescribe drugs for themselves. However, this is what is obtainable in this part of the world, where drugs are sold in the open market and even hawked in the streets. The survey result revealed that 81.1% of the respondents agreed that heat stress reduces the number of bricks they make in a day, this will affect their income and socio-economic life. 91.5% of the respondents feel very hot when working during heat wave. Occupational health is significantly impacted by heat stress, particularly for individuals engaged in physically demanding jobs in hot environments (Sario et al., 2023). This study underscores the urgent need for effective heat stress management strategies to protect the health and well-being of outdoor brick molders. These encompass physiological strain, thermal comfort, and overall health, as heat exposure can trigger a cascade of adverse effects, ranging from discomfort and

reduced productivity to severe health complications (Ginting & Pirgahayu, 2022; Somanathan et al., 2021). The convergence of these factors creates a pressing need for comprehensive interventions to mitigate heat stress among outdoor workers, thereby safeguarding their health and optimizing their work performance (Vaidyanathan et al., 2020).

The implementation of adaptation and mitigation measures emerges as crucial for safeguarding the current and future workforce against the escalating challenges posed by climate change, thus fostering improved worker health and productivity across various industries (Venugopal et al., 2015). Strategic adaptation options, such as modifying work schedules and implementing cooling technologies, necessitate policy

interventions and proactive planning (Day et al., 2018). The decline in global work productivity, equivalent to the loss of 80 million full-time jobs by 2030, underscores the substantial economic impact of heat stress, emphasizing the imperative for proactive measures to mitigate its effects and safeguard worker productivity (Rao et al., 2020). These findings highlight the necessity of enhancing prevention efforts to improve workers' awareness and resilience to occupational heat exposure, especially in regions anticipating increased heatwave frequency and intensity due to climate change (Sario et al., 2023). This converges with existing literature emphasizing the importance of educating workers about the risks of heat stress and providing them with the necessary tools and knowledge to protect themselves (Ireland et al., 2023).

Table 2 Questionnaire Results on Personal Experiences of Workers in Umuagwo (n = 106)

Survey Item	Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Is heat stress impact avoidable?	Yes	8	7.5
	No	98	92.5
Has heat stress had an impact on your body?	Yes	100	94.3
	No	6	5.7
Do you experience symptoms of heat stress?	Yes	102	96.2
	No	4	3.8
Have you experienced any heat stress-induced sickness?	Yes	102	96.2
	No	4	3.8
Have you taken self-medication due to heat stress?	Yes	68	64.2

	No	38	35.8
Does heat stress reduce the number of bricks you mold daily?	Yes	86	81.1
	No	20	18.9
How do you feel when working during a heat wave?	Hot	9	8.5
	Very Hot	97	91.5

Addressing urban heat necessitates context-specific strategies that consider both environmental and socioeconomic dimensions, offering a comprehensive framework for policymakers and practitioners to foster urban resilience and adaptation (Fu et al., 2024). The impact of excessive heat exposure on public health has been observed, with surplus mortality during heatwaves, and is expected to increase in areas already experiencing heat stress (Souverijns et al., 2022).

Implications for Occupational Health

The study findings highlight the urgent need for occupational health interventions to address heat stress among outdoor brick molders in Umuagwo and its environs, these include provision of adequate hydration as well as regular rest breaks in shaded areas; implementation of heat-stress monitoring programs; training on heat stress recognition and prevention; provision of appropriate PPEs. By implementing these interventions, it is possible to protect the health and well-being of outdoor brick molders and improve their productivity. The impact of heat on

labor productivity is particularly pronounced in sectors reliant on outdoor work, as increasing heat stress due to climate change affects labor supply and productivity (Nagurney, 2021). The vulnerability to heat stress is especially pronounced in primary economic sectors, where work is predominantly conducted outdoors, thus underscoring the need for targeted interventions and protective measures in these occupational environments (Morabito et al., 2020).

Limitations of the Study

A limitation of this study is that it only focused on outdoor brick molders in Umuagwo and its environs. Future studies should include other outdoor workers in different regions to provide a more comprehensive understanding of heat stress and its impact on occupational health. It is also important to note that this study relied on self-reported data, which may be subject to recall bias.

Conclusion

This study provides valuable insights into the prevalence of heat stress among outdoor

brick molders in Umuagwo and its environs. The findings highlight the need for urgent action to address heat stress and protect the health and well-being of these workers. The global burden of heat exposure on work capacity underscores the need for comprehensive strategies to protect workers' health and productivity. The absence or inadequate enforcement of regulations aimed at safeguarding workers exacerbates the risk of heat-related illnesses.

Recommendation

The findings underscore the need for implementing comprehensive heat management strategies in brick molding industries. These strategies should include:

The provision of readily accessible shade structures, such as canopies or shelters, at the worksite to reduce direct exposure to solar radiation.

Workers should be educated about the risks of heat stress and how to prevent it.

Ensuring that workers have access to an adequate supply of potable water and encouraging frequent hydration throughout the workday.

Further research should be conducted to develop and evaluate the effectiveness of different heat stress management interventions.

Policy Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following policy recommendations are proposed:

Implement heat action plans that include early warning systems, heat-health surveillance, and public awareness campaigns.

Enforce occupational health and safety regulations that protect outdoor workers from heat stress, such as mandatory rest breaks and access to cool water.

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Competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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